

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring
data into the Digital Twin Ocean

D2.4 Call for data grants_M2

311023

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D2.4 – Call for data grants_M2

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties

Keywords

Biodiversity; data; marine; grants; FSTP; open call

Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In significant advancements in Europe to collect, harmonise, and make available data on marine biodiversity, a large portion of data remains unavailable or inaccessible. This type of data is referred to as "sleeping data." To activate these sleeping data, a call for marine biodiversity (monitoring) data was launched on October 31st 2023. The primary goal of the call is to establish workflows and procedures that promote and facilitate the sharing of critical missing marine biodiversity data, and ultimately to facilitate sustained and long-term ingestion of previously inaccessible data into the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO) through publication in EMODnet Biology. Applications can be submitted until January 17th 2024, at 17h CET. The evaluation process is scheduled to occur from January 18th to February 8th, 2024. Eligible proposals will be selected based on multiple criteria, including their relevance, potential impact, ability to sustain data flow and automate processes, uniqueness, and overall proposal quality. Selected applicants will receive a Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) grant of up to €60.000.

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1. Call for marine biodiversity (monitoring) data

The (first) call for marine biodiversity (monitoring) data was launched on October 31st 2023. The primary goal of the call is to establish workflows and procedures that promote and facilitate the sharing of critical missing marine biodiversity data, and ultimately to facilitate sustained and long-term ingestion of previously inaccessible data into the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO) through publication in EMODnet Biology.

The full text describing all the call details can be found under 1.1. Call text. In close collaboration with WP6 (Trust-IT), this text was published on the DTO-BioFlow website, on the following page: <https://dto-bioflow.eu/marine-biodiversity-data-open-call>. In addition, a webform was set up by Trust-IT to receive the applications: <https://dto-bioflow.eu/marine-biodiversity-data-open-call-application>, containing the questions from the application form under 2. Annexes. The call is open for applications until January 17th 2024 at 17.00 CET.

The evaluation process is scheduled to occur from January 18th to February 8th, 2024. Eligible proposals will be selected based on multiple criteria, including their relevance, potential impact, ability to sustain data flow and automate processes, uniqueness, and overall proposal quality. The selected projects will receive up to €60.000 of financial support and will run for 12 months, from March 1st 2024 to February 28th 2025.

The call was announced through several social media platforms, website news sections and mailing lists. In addition, the DTO BioFlow project – with a dedicated presentation on the call – was presented during the Networking Fridays (November 24th, 2023), organised by the Atlantic International Research Centre (AIR Centre), an international collaborative framework to address global challenges and local priorities in the Atlantic Ocean. The session triggered a lot of interest towards the call and the DTO-BioFlow project in general. The session was recorded and can be found through <https://www.aircentre.org/netfridays-marine-biodiversity-15/>.

1.1. Call text

Background

The ocean and its biodiversity are essential to life on this planet. Comprehensive data on biodiversity, and related human and environmental pressures are crucial to understand its current state and how this may change. Protecting and restoring biodiversity is one of three objectives of the Horizon Europe Mission to restore our oceans and waters by 2030, enabling the EU to reach its Green Deal and Biodiversity 2030 targets. Identified as one of the Mission "enablers", the EU will build on "a digital knowledge system" to include a Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO) allowing simulation of 'what if' scenarios, advancing ocean knowledge, informing evidence-based policy and offering a range of societal applications.

The DTO-BioFlow project

To effectively replicate the ocean's ecology, the DTO requires sustained flows of data on biodiversity and associated pressures. While biodiversity data are being collected by myriad actors, using a wide variety of methods (including novel cost-effective monitoring technologies), not all these data become publicly available in a standardized format. DTO-BioFlow will activate these "sleeping" marine biodiversity data and enable the sustainable integration of data flows from various sources to EMODnet and into the [EDITO](#) infrastructure serving the EU DTO.

Combining sustained data flows, models and new algorithms, DTO-BioFlow will develop and integrate the biological component of the DTO, including new digital tools and services. Policy-relevant use cases, will demonstrate the benefit for marine ecosystems of continuous data streams flowing through EMODnet and usable by the EU DTO infrastructures and ultimate end-users. For more information on the DTO-BioFlow project, visit the [project's website](#).

Call for proposals

We are pleased to announce the launch of a call for marine biodiversity data holders who can contribute to the DTO-BioFlow project by establishing ingestion pipelines to the EU DTO and thereby increasing the flow of relevant biodiversity data. This Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) grant can provide support to do so, by funding resources as well as facilitating a data training workshop for the selected applicants.

Who can apply

Eligible beneficiaries for this call are data holders (international networks, citizen science networks, research institutes, universities, NGOs, etc.) who can facilitate sustained and long-term ingestion to the EU DTO of previously inaccessible data. Entities subject to [EU restrictive measures](#) under [Article 29 of the Treaty on the European Union \(TEU\)](#) and [Article 215 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU \(TFEU\)](#), are not eligible to participate as recipients of this FSTP. Please note that beneficiaries or affiliated partners of the DTO-BioFlow project cannot receive funding through this call.

Applicants should have a good command of English, must be eligible for participation in the EC Horizon Europe Framework Programme (see [list of participating countries](#)) and must ensure to follow the following obligations of the [Grant Agreement](#): Articles 12 (conflict of interest), 13 (confidentiality and security), 14 (ethics), 17.2 (visibility), 18 (specific rules for carrying out action), 19 (information) and 20 (recordkeeping). The DTO-BioFlow project coordinator will also ensure that the bodies mentioned in Article 25 (e.g. granting authority, OLAF, Court of Auditors (ECA), etc.) can exercise their rights also towards the recipients.

Applicants need to have the rights and permissions to work with the data, and bring these into the public domain under an open license.

The selected beneficiaries commit to carry out the following activities:

- Participate in the workshop which will provide training on how to reformat and quality control data conform international standards (see further) and make these available to EMODnet Biology, held in April 2024 in Paris or Ostend in week 15 or 17. In person attendance of at least one representative per selected beneficiary is required. It will also be possible to attend the training workshop online, in case multiple people per beneficiary want to attend the workshop but cannot all attend in person.
- Contribute to the flow of marine biodiversity data into the DTO, through developing data flow pipelines to EMODnet Biology. Setting up a data flow through intermediate data systems that already have or will in the near future have a direct data flow pipeline to EMODnet Biology (e.g. ICES, ETN) is also eligible.
- Ensure the data is formatted, standardized, and quality-controlled conforming to the relevant international standards (as demonstrated in the workshop) (e.g. using the Darwin Core standard for biodiversity data, OBIS-ENV-DATA as the preferred format, World Register of Marine Species, Marine Regions and BODC NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS) to standardize taxonomic names, location names and parameter names respectively, EMODnet Biology QC Check tool to perform quality checks).
- Ensure the data complies to Open Access, preferably under a Creative Commons [CC-BY license](#). If applicants plan to use any other license, this needs to be detailed in their application.
- Ensure that metadata and data will become available through EMODnet Biology.
- Provide short intermediary reports on their progress every four months, and a final report on the results at the end of the 12-month project.

Funding & eligibility

The maximum amount of financial support for each application is 60.000 EUR.

Half of the funding (50%) will be granted at the start of the project, the other half (50%) will be granted at the end of the project, which corresponds to a successful realization of the proposed activities.

List of costs that qualify for financial support:

- Personnel costs to execute the following types of activities:
 - Development of pipelines for data processing, reformatting, standardisation, transfer and publication
 - Development of data access API's (Application Programming Interface)
 - Data quality control
 - Data documentation and management (in accordance with FAIR principles)
- Travel costs to attend the data training workshop in April 2024, held in Paris or Ostend. At least one person and at most 2 persons per selected beneficiary should attend the workshop in person.

To be eligible to receive this grant, applications need to meet the following criteria:

- The data conform to the requirements of the project:
 - data is not readily available in the public domain, or is not in a standardized format. Updating existing datasets such as time series by enriching them with previously unavailable data (e.g. more recent data) is eligible.
 - data is marine biodiversity data: taxon occurrences, preferably linked to (a)biotic measurements retrieved at the same time and location. New biological data types from methods or sensors capable of species detection are eligible.
 - data are, for a substantial part, collected in European marine waters.
 - data can be published under an open license (preferably CC-BY).
- The data are helping the project to reach its overall goals:
 - filling important identified gaps in the biodiversity data coverage (e.g. poorly covered taxonomic groups, data poor regions, new data types)
 - facilitating a sustained and long-term ingestion and established data flow
 - mobilizing marine biodiversity (monitoring) data and data series
- The applicant is not a beneficiary or affiliated party to the DTO-BioFlow grant agreement.
- Good quality plan of action.
- Successful realisation of proposed activities.

Application process

October 31st 2023: Call opening

January 17th 2024: Call closing date

Single stage submission

Applicants should submit their application through the [Open Call webform](#) on the DTO-BioFlow website. If you do not already have an account on the DTO-Bioflow website, you will need to create one first to access the Open Call webform. You can save a draft of your Open Call application and return to it at a later date if necessary.

Timeline

January 18th – February 8th 2024: Evaluation and selection

February 12th 2024: Evaluation completed & beneficiaries informed

From March 1st 2024 to February 28th 2025 (12 months): Project implementation

April 2024, week 15 or week 17: Mandatory attendance of the planned workshop

June 30th 2024, October 31st 2024: Intermediary reports deadlines

February 28th 2025: Final report deadline

Assessment process

The assessment panel will rate all eligible proposals, taking into account the following criteria:

- **Relevance:** The proposal conforms to the requirements, goals and scope of the DTO-BioFlow project.
- **Impact:** What will be the estimated impact? Size/number, frequency, continuance, and range (temporal/geographic/taxonomic) of proposed dataset(s) will be considered, in combination with how much the proposed data contribute to filling gaps in the current biodiversity data landscape (gaps could be taxonomical, geographical, methodological, etc.).
- **Sustained data flow & automation:** the data flows set up within the project are designed to continue beyond the duration of the project, are as much as possible automated and the applicants are willing to commit to a long-term data flow, beyond the duration of their grant and the DTO-BioFlow project duration.
- **Uniqueness:** the proposal does not overlap with existing data pipelines and networks.
- **Excellence/proposal quality:** the proposed actions are realistic, feasible, well-defined and in balance with the requested financial support.

An initial ranking will be constructed based on this evaluation. Additional factors might impact the final list of third parties receiving funding, such as the amount of requested budget, similarity to a higher ranked proposal, ethical concerns and potential conflicts of interest.

Privacy

Personal data will be collected, processed and published in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679, also known as GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) as detailed in the DTO-Bioflow privacy policy.

Contact

Contact opencalls@dto-bioflow.eu for any questions about this call.

2. Annexes

Call for marine biodiversity (monitoring) data Application form

Applicant details

Contact details of the person representing the applicant

Name	
Function	
Organization	
Email	

Contact details of the official who authorized this application and who holds the responsibility to ensure the proper execution of the proposed project as detailed in this application

Name	
Function	
Organization	
Email	

General information

Title of the proposed project

Give a title for the proposed project in max. 150 characters.

Summary

Summarize the proposed project in max. 500 words.

Organization(s)

Give the name, type (e.g. NGO, scientific institution, government, etc.) and country of the organization(s)/institute(s)/entities involved in the implementation of the proposed project.

Current situation

Current data format & storage

Describe the current format of the data and where it is currently stored in max. 250 words.

Current challenges

Describe the current challenges for making these data openly available in max. 250 words.

Existing data flows

Describe if and how the data are part of any existing data flows in max. 250 words.

Project details

Project objectives

Describe the objectives of the proposed project in max. 750 words.

Methodology

Give a detailed description of the planned approach to accomplish the proposed project's objectives and how you plan to establish the data flow to EMODnet Biology in max. 1000 words.

Sustained data flow

Describe how the data flow is envisioned to continue beyond the end of the proposed project in max. 750 words.

Impact on existing data flows

Describe how the proposed project will impact existing data flows, if those exist, in max. 250 words.

Data details

Title(s) of the dataset(s) that will be part of the proposed project

Give the title(s) of the dataset(s) that will be part of the proposed project, together with their first contact person and – where possible – the citation of each dataset and where additional information on their metadata can be consulted (published report, web page, ...), in max. 500 words.

Current data description

Give a description of the currently existing data in max. 500 words. Make sure to include under which framework the data were originally collected (e.g. national monitoring, research project, historic data), temporal cover, geographic cover, taxonomic cover, dataset size (number of records), methodologies used to collect the data, and which parameters (e.g. counts, biomass) are included.

Future data description

Give a description of the future data expected to flow to DTO-BioFlow in max. 500 words. Make sure to include under which framework the data will be collected (e.g. national monitoring, research project, historic data), expected temporal cover, expected geographic cover, expected taxonomic cover, estimated expected order of magnitude of the dataset(s) (number of records), methodologies that will be used to collect the data, and which parameters (e.g. counts, biomass) will be included.

Relevance and impact

Describe the relevance and the impact of the proposed project in max. 500 words.

Budget

Indicate your planned budget (max. total €60.000). Only actual costs incurred by the recipients when implementing the supported activities will be reimbursed.

Personnel costs	Person Months (PM)	
	Average PM rate (€)	
	Total personnel costs (€)	
Travel and subsistence	Number of people who will attend the workshop physically (min. 1, max. 2)	
	Travel and subsistence costs (€)	
TOTAL grant amount (€)		

